

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF MUSEUMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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Abstract. *This article talks about tourism, museum tourism, the stages of its development, the role of museums in the development of tourism, their importance, the great achievements of world museums in this field, the role of museum tourism in the state economy. important and is a guide for those interested in this direction.*

Keywords: *tourism, economy, travel, natural monument, material and spiritual culture, museum tourism, exposition, excursion, museum shop, ICOM, tour operator, tourist program.*

Tourism (French: tour — walk, travel), tourism — travel; one of the types of active recreation. Tourism is defined as the departure (travel) of an individual from the place of permanent residence for a period of at least 1 year without engaging in paid activities in the destination (country) for health, educational, professional or other purposes.

In the language of the peoples of the world, the concept of "tourism" comes from the Latin word "tourmus" which means circular movement. Sometimes the French word "tour" is understood as a return trip with the purpose of returning to the place of departure. Concepts of tourism can be categorized as follows. Tourism is the temporary departure of people from their permanent residence for health, study or professional activities.

K. Richter, an international consultant on tourism issues, gives a general tariff to the field and describes it as a complex of interactions and situations related to permanent residence and being in a place other than the place of work, people's travel.

In this, K. Richter distinguishes specific directions of tourism research, and he organizes the activities of the entity that produces specific goods and services that are interesting for economic science and are produced for tourists. This is closely related to the organization of tourism demand.

The history of tourism dates back to the beginning of the 19th century. First, organized tourism from England to France was established (1815). The English priest Thomas Cook, who is considered the founder of tourism, organized the first railway tour in 1843. After that, he established his own tour company and in 1866 the first tour groups were sent to the United States. In the East, Ibn Battuta, an Arab traveler, started his journey at the age of 21 and traveled almost all the countries of East and North Africa on foot.

Nowadays, tourism has become popular in many countries of the world. Usually, Tourism is organized through tourism organizations along tourism routes. There are many types and forms of tourism (international tourism, domestic tourism, amateur tourism, organized tourism, local travel, long-distance travel, educational tourism, mountain climbing, water tourism, motor tourism, hiking tourism, sports tourism, etc.).

Tourism, including tourism, consists of activities of tourism organizers and intermediaries. Thus, tourism is a sector of the economy that needs to be managed and includes the activities of tourism organizers and intermediaries.

Travel and tourism are related concepts and represent a certain way of human life activity. This covers recreation, active or passive recreation, sports, environmental awareness, commerce, science, healing and much more. However, each time, a specific action that distinguishes travel from other types of activity is that a person temporarily goes to another place, country, continent, away from his permanent place of residence.

Travel is a general term that refers to the movement of people through time and space, regardless of their purpose. Expeditions, including military expeditions, are carried out by individuals with a separate, single goal and interest, which may include hundreds or even thousands of specialists, diplomats, migrants and emigrants. The crews of sea, air and other vehicles cannot stay at home for years. Thus, travel can be lifestyle, work, leisure.

Although tourism is a type of travel, it has its own characteristics and a certain description, and the person who participates in it is called a tourist. Unlike travel, tourism is a category that is strongly influenced by economics and politics, and on top of that, it has the duality of an internal natural phenomenon.

Museum tourism is a special type of tourism, its characteristic feature is the use of the tourist potential of museums and the areas adjacent to them.

The museum is a cultural-educational and scientific-research institution designed to study, preserve and use natural monuments, material and spiritual culture, and introduce citizens to the national and world historical and cultural heritage. According to their profile, museums are divided into the following types: historical, archeological, local history, natural, literary, artistic, ethnographic, technical, network and so on. In 1946, the international organization ICOM (International Council of Museums) was established to support and develop the activities of museums. This organization includes more than 27,000 members from 115 countries and closely cooperates with UNESCO and other international organizations.

Cooperation between museums and tourism is based on the formation of a system of historical, cultural and natural areas. The development of these regions is ensured by the accumulation of historical and cultural heritage in museums, which serves as a factor of socio-cultural and touristic development of individual regions. Organizers of museum tourism have a number of specific tasks: to determine the tourist specialty of the museum and to form a constant flow of tourists to the museum, to create a tourist program and route, to create a package of advertising products, to find new sources and financing.

Museum tourism is a specific activity of museums in the field of cultural tourism in the production and sale of various tourist products of a museum nature: creation of expositions, organization of internal and external excursions, existence of museum stores. This direction of tourism appeared relatively recently - in the 1970s in the West and in the mid-1990s in Russia, museums began to seek self-determination, new ways of development and a new budget for attracting funds. included in the search for resources, including participation in tourist activities. The urgency of the revival of interest in visiting museums among tourists is due to the change of their exterior and interior space, which should attract visitors.

Today, the museum is in the conditions of market competition, and the museum product is in the service economy. During the last 10-15 years, a real "boom" was observed in the field of museum construction all over the world. Today, in many cities, the projects of radical expansion and reconstruction of existing museums are being considered, and new museums are being established, from ancient to very modern, which preserve and display art in order to attract tourists.

A lot of money is allocated to the development of museums, including the construction of museums. This institution, which seems conservative and calm, with great speed like a large modern corporation, is integrated into the processes of modern globalization and receives an unimaginable number of visitors. Museum tourism is certainly not a traditional activity of museums at first. In Russia, this phenomenon is relatively recent - in the mid-1990s, at a time when museums, like other cultural institutions, were in a situation of self-determination, new ways of development and the search for new non-budgetary sources of funding. appeared., including through participation in tourism activities.

Museum tourism, by its essence, is a unique activity of museums in the field of educational tourism for the production and sale of various tourist products of a museum nature (creating expositions, organizing internal and external excursions, museum shops, etc.). In some cases, it operates to organize a tourist cycle (accommodation, meals, transfer, information provision, etc.).

Museum tourism is a component of cultural-educational tourism and includes mandatory visits to museums, historical city centers, sightseeing of cultural attractions, archaeological excavations. is based on the idea of showing (covering) history and culture in a comprehensive way, especially according to the uniqueness and composition of museum collections.

The main processes related to the creation of museum and tourism products:
interpret the cultural heritage of the area;
development of specific museum and tourism creativity (creative solutions).

Museum tourism is aimed at working with individual tourists or small groups of independent travelers, as well as with organized groups, without resorting to the services of travel companies. Accordingly, museums can occupy different positions in the field of tourism.

When it comes to independent tourists, the museum can take the position of a tour operator - in fact, the host, together with other local partners (DC, local community, municipalities, etc.), provides its own tourist cycle, including a tourist trip. Organizes cultural programs, entertainment, etc. In organized groups, the museum works as one of the elements of external cultural and touristic programs (routes) working on the basis of a contract with certain tourist agencies.

Cooperation between museums and tourism is based on the formation of a system of historical, cultural and natural areas.

Museum tourism is a unique type of tourism, its distinctive feature is the use of the tourist potential of museums and their adjacent areas. Museum tourism as a system of mutual cooperation of museums and tourist companies in the field of cultural tourism provides the following:

- 1) development of a prospective program unifying the activities of museums;
- 2) development and implementation of museum tours;
- 3) inclusion of cultural events in tourist programs;
- 4) creation of effective forms of cooperation between museums and tourist organizations (tour operator + museum);
- 5) introduction of new forms of service to tourists: single museum ticket, city visitor card;
- 6) use of flexible pricing policy.

Abroad, for example, in Paris, a museum card (Carte Musees-Monuments) was introduced, which is sold at tourist offices, metro stations, FNAC stores and museums themselves. With it, you can visit 70 museums and historical monuments in and around Paris. Admission to museums is free for children under 18 years of age. The price of a 1-day museum card is about 15 euros, for 3 days - 30 euros, for 5 days - 45 euros. With an average price of a museum ticket of 7.50 euros,

buying a museum card is very convenient. The only thing is that the museum card does not allow access to temporary exhibitions.

In the Canadian province of Quebec, the museum card was launched in 2009. Costing \$50 plus tax, it gives you one-time admission to ten museums within three days of purchase. The card entitles you to two days of free travel in city land transport, discounts in stores - the list of possibilities is quite long.

Such tourist cards are used in many countries.

Based on the interests and wishes of tourists, various tourist programs are being developed. Tourism in foreign countries with developed tourist infrastructure and huge historical and cultural potential cannot be imagined without the use of marketing. Museums are an attraction for tourists. They work closely with the tourism industry through promotion, destination analysis and pricing. Through the tourism industry, the museum connects with profitable businesses such as hotels and tour operators to promote their products. Pooling of resources contributes greatly to the improvement of additional advertising and participation.

The brand and image of a certain region plays an important role in the development of museum tourism abroad. To attract visitors, various legends are often told about the events that happened in this area. The ability to properly apply museum marketing and management can attract many tourists.

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